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Abstract: A steady-state mathematical model of a vertically stacked forward feed multi-effect distillation (MED) plant has been carried out using a number of simplifying assumptions. The model has been developed taking into consideration the same design and operational characteristics as the pilot MED plant at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), in the southeast of Spain. It is a forward feed MED plant with preheaters, which uses low steam temperature coming from a parabolic-trough solar collector field as the thermal energy source. The pilot plant has a special distillate distribution for increased energy recovery which has also been taken into account in the model. This model is simple to implement and suitable for its use in optimization of water production in power and water cogeneration systems. The results of the model have been compared with the experimental data of the pilot plant showing a maximum prediction error of 9 %

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Editor
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Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Desalination journal.

Title:

“Steady State Model for Multi-Effect Distillation. Case Study: Plataforma Solar de Almería MED Pilot Plant”

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Yours, sincerely

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Highlights

- A steady-state mathematical model of a MED plant has been carried out
- The model takes into account the same characteristics as the pilot MED plant at PSA
- The pilot plant has a special distillate distribution for increased energy recovery
- The validation of the model resulted in a maximum prediction error of 9 %

Steady State Model for Multi-Effect Distillation

Case Study: Plataforma Solar de Almería MED Pilot Plant

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Abstract

A steady-state mathematical model of a vertically stacked forward feed multi-effect distillation (MED) plant has been carried out using a number of simplifying assumptions. The model has been developed taking into consideration the same design and operational characteristics as the pilot MED plant at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), in the southeast of Spain. It is a forward feed MED plant with preheaters, which uses low steam temperature coming from a parabolic-trough solar collector field as the thermal energy source. The pilot plant has a special distillate distribution for increased energy recovery which has also been taken into account in the model. This model is simple to implement and suitable for its use in optimization of water production in power and water cogeneration systems. The results of the model have been compared with the experimental data of the pilot plant showing a maximum prediction error of 9 %.

Keywords: Multi-effect distillation; modeling; energy recovery

1. Introduction

The importance of supplying potable water can hardly be overstressed and the need for development and implementation of a wide variety of desalination technologies continues to grow. Desalination can be achieved by using several techniques. These may be classified into the following categories: (i) phase-change or thermal processes, of which multi-stage flash (MSF) and multi-effect distillation (MED) are the most widespread industrial applications, and (ii) membrane or single-phase processes, of which reverse osmosis (RO) is the most common. In the thermal processes, thermal energy may be obtained from a conventional fossil-fuel source or from a non-conventional source like nuclear energy or renewable energy (e.g., solar). Despite the vast improvements to reverse osmosis in recent years, there is still a need for thermal methods of desalination. The latter have several advantages with respect to membrane processes: their easier operation and maintenance, which make their installation possible in countries lacking in experienced personnel, the higher purity of the distillate produced and their capability to deal with harsh feed waters of high temperature and salinity or even with contamination.

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4 Additionally, thermal desalination processes using solar energy as the source of heat match
5 perfectly with the fact that many countries suffering from fresh water shortage have abundant
6 seawater resources and high solar radiation levels. While MSF is the dominant type of large-
7 scale thermal desalination technologies currently in use, MED is more efficient from a
8 thermodynamic and heat transfer point of view and is currently receiving considerable attention
9 as a strong competitor to MSF, especially in the Middle East-Arabian Gulf area [1]. The MED
10 process is characterized by lower energy consumption ($\sim 2 \text{ kWh/m}^3$) compared to the MSF
11 process ($\sim 4 \text{ kWh/m}^3$). Additionally, the top operating temperature of a MED plant is lower than
12 for the MSF technology, which maximizes the electricity production when using the low grade
13 exhaust heat from power station turbines as the primary heat source for the desalination process.
14 MED systems are established worldwide, especially within the Arabian Gulf with capacities
15 ranging from 1,500-800,000 m^3/day [2].
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22 Despite the advantages that MED processes have in comparison to membrane technologies, their
23 main disadvantage is the high energy consumption, especially as compared to the minimum work
24 of separation [3], which suggests that further research on this and other technologies is needed in
25 order to lower the cost and increase the availability of potable water. The use of MED plants is
26 becoming more relevant driven by the possibility of integrating them into thermal power plants
27 to produce fresh water and electricity by a cogeneration system [3, 4]. This integration can
28 produce water at lower costs than if both products were generated independently [5]. In order to
29 increase the energy optimization of MED plants, mathematical modeling and computer
30 simulations of different designs of MED plants are needed. Numerous MED models have been
31 developed and published in the scientific literature. El-Sayed and Silver [6], developed one of the
32 earliest models for a forward feed MED, in which they calculated the performance ratio and heat
33 transfer areas through several simplifying thermodynamic assumptions. El-Dessouky et al. [7-10]
34 analyzed different MED configurations including the parallel flow, the parallel/cross flow and
35 systems combined with a thermal vapor compressor (TVC) or mechanical vapor compressor
36 (MVC). Darwish et al. [11, 12] also developed a MED model and analyzed various
37 configurations, finding the tradeoff between performance ratio and required heat transfer area.
38 El-Allawy [13] examined how the energy efficiency of an MED (with and without TVC) system
39 varied with the top brine temperature (TBT) and the number of effects. Results revealed that the
40 increase of the number of effects from 3 to 6 resulted in an increase of the gained output ratio
41 (GOR) by nearly two-fold. Aly and El-Figi [14] developed a steady state mathematical model to
42 study the performance of a forward feed MED plant and found that the performance ratio
43 depends significantly more on the number of effects than on the top brine temperature. Ameri et
44 al. [15] studied the effect of design parameters on MED system specifications and found that the
45 optimum performance depends on an optimum number of effects which itself depends on sea
46 water salinity, feed water temperature, and temperature differences between effects.
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58 Other authors have published models of MED plants using renewable energy as the heat source
59 of the unit. El Nashar and Qamhiyeh ([16-18]) presented a mathematical simulation of the
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4 operation at transient and steady state of a solar MED plant located in Abu Dhabi (UAE). To
5 solve the model, empirical correlations of the heat transfer coefficients of the plant components
6 were obtained from experimental data of the MED pilot plant. It was found that the model was
7 able to predict the distillate production and specific heat consumption at each operating condition
8 with reasonably accuracy. Leblanc et al. [19] implemented the model of a MED pilot plant which
9 is fed by hot water from a solar pond. The model was used for the plant design and the
10 agreement between the experimental and simulation results was found to be good. Yilmaz and
11 Söylemez [20] developed a model of a forward feed MED plant using hybrid renewable energy
12 sources (solar and wind). The model was used for simulations for a case study of a plant located
13 in Turkey. Reddy et al. [21] proposed a transient model of a MED plant coupled to flat plate
14 collectors. This model was used to optimize the plant configuration studying the effect of several
15 design and operational parameters on its performance.
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22 This paper is focused on modeling an innovative solar MED pilot plant with increased energy
23 efficiency that has been operating successfully at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA). The plant
24 uses low steam temperature coming from parabolic-trough solar collectors as thermal energy
25 source and has an innovative distribution of distillate collection for recovering its sensible heat.
26 There are no models in the literature that contemplate this innovative configuration. The paper
27 describes a detailed model of the plant, showing its validation with experimental values and an
28 assessment of the variation of the plant performance and the total distillate production with
29 several operating plant parameters.
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34 **2. MED plant description**

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36 The desalination plant of PSA is a forward feed MED unit manufactured and delivered by
37 ENTROPIE in 1987. It has 14 cells/effects in a stack arrangement at decreasing pressures and
38 temperatures from the first effect (on the top) to the last one [22, 23]. It has 13 preheaters, each
39 one located next to each effect, to increase the seawater temperature while it is being pumped up
40 to the first effect. The temperature increase in the preheater is the result of the latent heat of
41 condensation of part of the vapor generated in each effect.
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46 The flow diagram of the process is shown in Fig. 1. The seawater (feed water) is pumped and
47 preheated through the preheaters into the first effect, where it is deposited over a perforated tray
48 falling then in a thin film over a horizontal-tube bundle. The first effect works with low-pressure
49 saturated steam provided by a parabolic trough collector solar field. The heating steam flows
50 inside the tube bundle and releases its latent heat to sprayed feed water, evaporating part of it.
51 The vapor generated in the first effect flows through a wire mesh demister that removes the
52 entrained brine droplets, some of which will be condensed on the preheater. The rest flows inside
53 the tube bundle of the second effect. In the second effect, the vapor transfers its latent heat to the
54 brine that is falling by gravity from the 1st effect. The vapor that condenses is mixed with the
55 distillate of the first pre-heater, obtaining the first distillate of the process. The same process is
56 repeated in the rest of effects, being the vapor produced in the previous effect the thermal energy
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4 source of the effect. In each effect, as in the first one, part of the vapor generated is used to
5 preheat the seawater that flows through the preheaters.
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8 Starting from the second effect, besides the vapor formed by seawater boiling, as soon as the
9 brine is sprayed into the vapor space, vapor is also generated by a flashing process at the vapor
10 temperature and pressure of the effect . Finally, the vapor produced in the last effect (by boiling
11 and flashing) is condensed in the final condenser, transferring the latent heat of evaporation to
12 the seawater that is passing into the tube bundle, which increases its temperature. A part of this
13 seawater (name feed water) is pumped to the first effect passing through the preheaters and the
14 rest is rejected to the sea again.
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19 The total distillate production of the plant consists of the vapor condensed in each effect and in
20 the preheaters plus the distillate generated in the final condenser. As an energy optimization
21 strategy, the distillate goes directly to the next effect, but in some effects (4, 7, 10 and 13) a
22 fraction of the distillate is distributed as shown in Fig. 1.
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25 The vacuum system consists of two hydro ejectors, one for effects 2 and 7 and the second one for
26 the final condenser. This system makes the initial vacuum in the plant and also removes the air
27 (possible penetration due to non-perfect air tightness) and the non-condensable gases.
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30 **3. Methodology**

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32 MATLAB software is used as environment to solve the mathematical model accounting for the
33 features of the MED-PSA plant. In order to simplify the model calculations, some assumptions
34 have been considered:
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- 37 • Steady state operation.
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- 39 • Distillate that passes from one effect to the next one leaves each effect at the subcooled
40 region 2 °C cooler than the inlet vapor temperature in the effect, after transferring its
41 sensible heat to the feed water.
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- 43 • The flashing process of the distillate has not been taken into consideration, except in the
44 final condenser.
- 45 • The thermodynamic losses have been assumed to be 1 °C as a real design value, which
46 includes 0.5 °C for non-equilibrium allowance (NEA).
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- 48 • 2 % of the vapor generated in 2th and 7th effect, and in the final condenser, is extracted by
49 the vacuum system
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- 51 • Isothermal physical properties have been considered for all cases.
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56 To develop the model, the MED system has been divided into three components: the preheaters,
57 the effects and the final condenser. Likewise, the effects of the MED system have been
58 considered in three different groups which are modeled individually. The first effect (named as
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group G1), the effects from 2 to N (named group G2) and the final condenser (named group G3). G2 is distinguished between three subgroups, namely: G2-1 for effects 2, 5, 8, 11 & 14; G2-2 for effects 3, 4, 6, 9 & 12; and G2-3 for effects 7, 10 & 13.

3.1. Preheaters

Fig. 2 shows a flow diagram of a typical preheater (# i) where the relevant variables that characterize the preheater's inlet and outlet streams are presented. The equations for all preheaters are mathematically similar among all them.

The energy balance and the heat transfer rate for the preheaters are the following:

- **Energy balance:** The latent heat that is released in the condensation process is used to heat the seawater flowing through the bundle tube of the preheater.

$$M_{vh,i} \lambda_{vh,i} = M_f C_{pf} (T_{ph,i+1} - T_{ph,i}) \quad (1)$$

- **Heat transfer equation:** The log mean temperature difference ($LTMD_{ph}$) method is used for the heat transfer rate.

$$Q_{ph,i} = A_{ph,i} U_{ph,i} LTMD_{ph,i} = M_f C_p (T_{ph,i+1} - T_{ph,i}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where: } LTMD_{ph,i} = \frac{(T_{v,i} - T_{ph,i+1}) - (T_{v,i} - T_{ph,i})}{\ln \left(\frac{T_{v,i} - T_{ph,i+1}}{T_{v,i} - T_{ph,i}} \right)} \quad (3)$$

The overall heat transfer coefficient ($U_{ph,i}$) is calculated using the following correlation from El-Dessouky and Ettouney [7]:

$$U_{ph,i} = 1.7194 + 3.2063 \cdot 10^{-3} T_{v,i} + 1.5971 \cdot 10^{-5} T_{v,i}^2 - 1.9918 \cdot 10^{-7} T_{v,i}^3 \quad (4)$$

3.2. Effects

First effect (G1)

Fig. 3 shows the flow diagram of the 1st effect. The mass, salt and energy balances, and the heat transfer equation are shown below:

- **Mass balance:** Part of the feed stream is evaporated (vapor stream) and the rest is concentrated in salts (brine stream).

$$M_f = M_{gb,1} + M_{b,1} \quad (5)$$

- Salt balance: Salinity of the brine stream leaving the effect is found through a salt balance in which it is assumed that the vapor formed by boiling is pure.

$$X_f M_f = X_{b,1} M_{b,1} \quad (6)$$

- Energy balance: The latent heat that is released in the condensation of the low pressure steam is used to heat the feed to the boiling point and then evaporate part of it.

$$M_{gb,1} \lambda_{gb,1} = M_s \lambda_s - M_f C_{pf} (T_{b,1} - T_f) \quad (7)$$

- Heat transfer equation The heat transfer rate (Q_s) is equal to the change in enthalpy associated with the condensation of the vapor (λ_s).

$$Q_s = U_{eff,1} \cdot A_{eff,1} \cdot (T_s - T_{b,1}) = M_s \lambda_s \quad (8)$$

The overall heat transfer coefficient ($U_{eff,1}$) is calculated using the following correlation from El-Dessouky and Ettouney [7]:

$$U_{eff,1} = 1.9695 + 1.2057 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot T_{b,1} - 8.5989 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot T_{b,1}^2 + 2.5651 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot T_{b,1}^3 \quad (9)$$

In the first effect, unlike the rest, the distillate produced is not considered as part of the distillate production of the plant, since it is generated from the external thermal energy source required in this effect. Therefore:

$$M_d(1) = 0 \quad (10)$$

Also, in this effect the feed water enters at a temperature which is below that of saturation (subcooled), so no vapor is generated by flashing:

$$M_{gf}(1) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Effects from 2 to N (Group G2)

The mass, salt and energy balances corresponding to the flashing process for the G2 group are mathematically similar among all the effects. The equations of the mass balance, heating source and the heat transfer equation in the tube bundle are also mathematically similar among all the effects of Group 2. Therefore, all these equations are common to all the subgroups of G2 group.

Only the energy balance in the tube bundle and the distillate produced in the effect will be analyzed for each subgroup of group G2 (G2-1, G2-2 and G2-3) and are showed below.

Subgroup G2-1

Fig. 4 shows a flow diagram of one effect of the subgroup G2-1.

- Energy balance: The latent heat released in the condensation of the vapor from the previous effect and the sensible heat released from the distillate coming from the pre-heater are used for the evaporation of the brine.

$$M_{gb,i} \lambda_{gb,i} = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} + M_{b,i} C_p (T_{b,i}' - T_{b,i}) + M_{vh,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i-1}') \quad (12)$$

- Distillate produced: The distillate leaving the effect is the sum of the vapor condensed from the previous effect and the distillate from the previous preheater.

$$M_{d,i} = M_{v,i} + M_{vh,i-1} \quad (13)$$

Subgroup G2-2

The scheme diagram is shown in Fig. 5, presenting the effect's inlet and outlet streams for this subgroup.

- Energy balance: In this case, an additional term corresponding to the sensible heat released from the distillate coming from the previous effect ($M_{d,i-1} C_p (T_{d,i-1} - T_{d,i-1}')$) needs to be added to equation (12).

$$M_{gb,i} \lambda_{gb,i} = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} + M_{b,i} C_p (T_{b,i}' - T_{b,i}) + M_{vh,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i-1}') + M_{d,i-1} C_p (T_{d,i-1} - T_{d,i-1}') \quad (14)$$

- Distillate produced: The distillate coming from the previous effect ($M_{d,i-1}$) joins the vapor condensed from the previous effect and the distillate from the previous pre-heater.

$$M_{d,i} = M_{v,i} + M_{vh,i-1} + M_{d,i-1} \quad (15)$$

Subgroup G2-3

The flow diagram of a representative effect of this group, showing the inlet and outlet streams is presented in Fig. 6.

- Energy balance: In this case, additional sensible heat ($M_{da,i} C_p (T_{dm,i-3} - T_{dm,i-3}')$) is released by the distillate coming from further effects ($M_{da,i}$).

$$M_{gb,i} \lambda_{gb,i} = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} + M_{b,i} C_p (T_{b,i}' - T_{b,i}) + M_{vh,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i-1}') + M_{d,i-1} C_p (T_{d,i-1} - T_{d,i-1}') + M_{da,i} C_p (T_{dm,i-3} - T_{dm,i-3}') \quad (16)$$

- Distillate produced: Taking into account the additional distillate coming from further effects ($M_{da,i}$), the distillate produced from these effects is given by the following equation:

$$M_{d,i} = M_{v,i} + M_{vh,i-1} + M_{d,i-1} + M_{da,i} \quad (17)$$

On the other hand, as an energy optimization strategy, the MED-PSA plant has a special distillate distribution shown in Fig. 7. Energy and mass balances through the mixers are shown below.

- Mass balance (for Mixers 7, 10 and 13):

$$M_{dm,i} = M_{dr,i} + M_{d,i} \quad (18)$$

$$M_{dr,i-3} = 0 \quad \text{for Mixer 7} \quad (19)$$

$$M_{dr,i} = M_{d,i-3} + M_{dr,i-3} - M_{da,i} \quad (20)$$

- Mass balance (for Mixer 14):

$$M_{dm,i} = M_{dm,i-1} + M_{d,i} \quad (21)$$

- Energy balance (for Mixers 7, 10, 13):

$$M_{dr}(i) \cdot C_p \cdot T_{dm}(i-3) + M_d(i) \cdot C_p \cdot T_d(i) = M_{dm}(i) \cdot C_p \cdot T_{dm}(i) \quad (22)$$

$$T_{dm,i-3} = T_{d,i-3} \quad \text{for Mixer 7} \quad (23)$$

- Energy balance for Mixer 14:

$$M_{dm,i-1} C_p T_{dm,i-1} + M_{d,i} C_p T_{d,i} = M_{dm,i} C_p T_{dm,i} \quad (24)$$

The mass, salt and energy balances corresponding to the flashing process occurring in all G2 group effects are shown below:

- Mass balance: For this particular case, part of the brine flashes ($M_{gf,i}$) as entering the effect and the rest ($M'_{b,i}$) is sprayed over the tube bundle:

$$M_{b,i} = M_{gf,i} + M'_{b,i} \quad (25)$$

- Salt balance: As in all the cases, the vapor formed is assumed to be pure.

$$X_{b,i-1}M_{b,i-1} = X'_{b,i}M'_{b,i} \quad (26)$$

- **Energy balance:** The brine coming from the previous effect enters each effect at a higher temperature than the one corresponding to the equilibrium temperature at the pressure of this effect. As a result, it flashes and generates steam at the vapor temperature ($T_{v,i}$), and subsequently the temperature of the un-evaporated water decreases from T_b to T'_b .

$$M_{gf,i}\lambda_{gf,i} = M_{b,i-1}C_p(T_{b,i-1} - T'_{b,i}) \quad (27)$$

The temperature of the un-evaporated brine (T'_b) is lower than the vapor temperature (T_v) by the non-equilibrium allowance (NEA), which is a measure of the flashing process [4]:

$$T'_{b,i} = T_{v,i} - NEA_i \quad (28)$$

The equations of the mass balance, heating source and the heat transfer equation taking place in the tube bundle are the following:

- **Mass balance:** In this case, part of the un-evaporated brine after the flashing process is evaporated ($M_{gb,i}$) and the rest ($M_{b,i}$) leaves the effect more concentrated in salts:

$$M'_{b,i} = M_{gb,i} + M_{b,i} \quad (29)$$

- **Salt balance:**

$$X'_{b,i}M'_{b,i} = X_{b,i}M_{b,i} \quad (30)$$

- **Heat transfer equation:** In each effect, the vapor coming from the previous effect condenses completely while evaporating by boiling the brine sprayed over the tubes. The heat transfer rate (Q_{eff}) is equal to the change in enthalpy associated with the condensation of the vapor (λ_v).

$$Q_{eff,i} = U_{eff,i}A_{eff,i}(T_{v,i-1} - T_{b,i}) = M_{v,i}\lambda_{v,i-1} \quad (31)$$

Equation (9) is used to calculate the overall heat transfer coefficient ($U_{eff,i}$) for all the effects.

Finally, the heating source in each effect consists of the total vapor generated by boiling and flashing minus the vapor consumed in the preheater, as shown in the following equation:

$$M_{v,i} = M_{gb,i-1} + M_{gf,i-1} - M_{vh,i-1} \quad (32)$$

3.3 Final condenser

Fig. 8 shows a scheme diagram of the final condenser, representing the inlet and outlet streams.

The energy, mass balance and heat transfer equation for the condenser are similar to those ones for the preheaters.

- Energy balance:

$$M_{sw} C_p (T_{cw,out} - T_{cw,in}) = (M_{gb,N} + M_{gf,N} + M_{df}) \lambda_{vc} \quad (33)$$

- Mass balance:

$$M_{prod} = M_{gb,N} + M_{gf,N} + M_{dm,14} \quad (34)$$

- Heat transfer equation:

$$Q_c = A_c \cdot U_c \cdot LTMD_c = M_{sw} C_p (T_{cw,out} - T_{cw,in}) \quad (35)$$

$$\text{where: } LTMD_c = \frac{(T_{v,N} - T_{cw,in}) - (T_{v,N} - T_{cw,out})}{\ln \left(\frac{T_{v,N} - T_{cw,in}}{T_{v,N} - T_{cw,out}} \right)} \quad (36)$$

The overall heat transfer coefficient (U_c) is calculated by equation(4).

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Plant performance

Once the model is implemented and the simulation run, the plant performance is evaluated by the following parameters: the Gain Output Ratio (GOR), which is defined as the mass flow rate of distillate produced per consumed heating steam rate, the recovery ratio (RR), which is the ratio of the distillate product flow rate to the feed flow rate supplied, and the specific area (sA), which is defined as the ratio of the total heat transfer area (for effects, preheaters and final condenser) to the distillate production. They are calculated as follows:

$$GOR = \frac{M_{prod}}{M_s} \quad (37)$$

$$RR = \frac{M_{prod}}{M_f} \quad (38)$$

$$sA = \frac{\sum A_{eff} + \sum A_{ph} + A_c}{M_{prod}} \quad (39)$$

4.2. Validation of the model

The model has been validated by comparing experimental data of the MED-PSA plant to those obtained from the simulations run from the mathematical model. As input variables, some of the design values provided by the manufacturer have been used. The values of the input variables are specified in Tables 1 and 2 and they are average values of the experimental data. The output variables that have been compared with each other are: the accumulated vapor in each effect, that is the sum of the vapor generated by boiling and flashing (M_{fv}), the brine leaving each effect (M_b), the total distillate water production (M_{prod}), the seawater inlet mass flow rate in the condenser (M_{sw}), the Gain Output Ratio (GOR), the Recovery Ratio (RR) and the heat transfer areas (effects, A_{eff} , preheaters, A_{ph} , condenser, A_c). The results are shown in Table 3 and 4, and Figs. 9 and 10. The relative error for predicting the outlet variables ranges between 1 % and 9 %. The maximum error corresponds to the mass flow rate in the condenser (see Table 4). It can be due to the fact that this mass flow rate is not kept constant during each experiment because the plant does not operate at the seaside. Seawater is simulated in large storages that feed the plant. As a consequence, the temperature of the seawater entering the condenser tube bundle ($T_{cw,in}$) can increase during the experiment. When this happens, the mass flow rate in the condenser is increased to keep the vapor temperature on the inside constant. This also results in a larger difference between the model and experimental values of the heat transfer area of the condenser. On the other hand, it is also seen in Table 4 that the heat transfer areas of the effects and preheaters resulting from the model do not match those of the pilot plant. This is due to the fact that the plant has the same areas whereas in the model there is not that restriction. The heat transfer areas shown from the calculation are average values for all the effects and preheaters.

4.3 Parametric study

In this section, the results of a parametric study using the computational model are presented. It will be useful for predicting how parameters that assess the performance of the plant (like the GOR , the specific area and the total distillate production) are affected by changes in design variables, namely: the brine temperature in the first effect, $T_b(1)$, and the temperature difference in the condenser, $\Delta T_{c...}$. The former is representative of the change in the rest of the effects, and affects the GOR and the specific area. The latter is representative of the energetic performance of the condenser and has a strong influence in the total distillate production.

Firstly, the effect of the brine temperature in the first effect on the GOR is shown in Fig. 11. For these simulations, the heating steam temperature (T_s) was assumed as 5°C over the brine

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4 temperature in the first effect ($T_b(1)$), the feed water temperature in the first effect (T_f) 1.7 °C
5 lower than the vapor temperature in the first effect ($T_v(1)$), and the vapor temperature in each
6 effect ($T_v(i)$) 1 °C lower than the brine temperature in each effect due to the thermodynamic
7 losses. . The rest of input variables values shown in Table 1 and 2 were maintained constant. In
8 this Figure, it can be seen that the *GOR* decreases linearly with the increase of the top brine
9 temperature. Increasing the top brine temperature while keeping the heating steam mass flow rate
10 (M_s) constant means a decrease in the heat transfer rate in the first effect (Q_s), which makes the
11 amount of vapor generated in the first effect decrease. As a consequence, a lower amount of
12 vapor is obtained in the rest of effects decreasing total distillate production. Since the decrease in
13 the total distillate production is higher than the decrease in the heat transfer rate, the *GOR*
14 decreases with the top brine temperature as shown in this Figure. Secondly, Fig. 12 shows the
15 variation of the specific area (*sA*) with the top brine temperature. For these simulations, the same
16 input variable conditions as in the previous ones were considered. It can be seen that the specific
17 area decreases with the increase of the top brine temperature. Increasing the brine temperature in
18 the first effect makes the temperature difference between the vapor and the brine temperature in
19 the previous and next effects, respectively, increase. As a result, the heat transfer area of the
20 effects decrease and therefore the specific area since the rest of heat transfer areas (preheaters
21 and condenser) are hardly affected. Finally, the effect of the temperature difference in the
22 condenser on the total distillate production is shown in Fig. 13. In these simulations, all the input
23 variables values shown in Table 1 and 2 were maintained constant. It is observed that the total
24 distillate production increases with the increase of the temperature difference in the condenser.
25 Keeping the feed water temperature constant makes the temperature difference between
26 preheaters decrease, which results in a drop of the vapor mass flow rate going to each preheater.
27 This fact allows the mass flow rate of heating steam per each effect increases (as seen in
28 equation (32), and therefore the vapor generated in each one. It results in an increase of the total
29 distillate production of the plant.
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41 **5. Conclusions**

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43 A model of a vertically stacked forward feed MED plant with an advanced system for energy
44 recovery, has been developed based on the design of the pilot MED plant located at the PSA.
45 The model has been validated by comparing with experimental data from real plant operation.
46 The model is able to predict with good accuracy (relative errors lower than 9%) the following
47 variables: total distillate water production, seawater inlet mass flow rate in the condenser,
48 performance ratio, Recovery Ratio, heat transfer areas of the effects, preheaters and condenser,
49 accumulated vapor generated by boiling and flashing process and brine mass leaving each effect.
50 The model represents not only the behavior of the MED-PSA plant but it can be used as a tool to
51 simulate further optimizations of MED plants. This is especially relevant for assessing the
52 integration of MED plants in cogeneration CSP+MED systems, which have the opportunity to
53 lower the cost and increase the availability of potable water comparing to RO units.
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4 **Symbols**

5 A Heat transfer area, m²
6 C_p Specific heat, kJ/kg°C
7 M Mass flow rate, kg/s
8 M' Mass flow rate by flashing process, kg/s
9 N Total number of effects
10 NEA Non-equilibrium allowance, °C
11 PR Performance Ratio
12 Q Heat transfer rate, kW
13 T Temperature, °C
14 T' Temperature by flashing process, °C
15 U Overall heat transfer coefficient, kW/m²°C
16 X Salt concentration, g/kg
17 TTL Thermodynamic losses, °C
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22 **Greek**

23 λ Latent heat of evaporation, kJ/kg
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26 **Subscript**

27 b Reject brine
28 v Vapor
29 c Condenser
30 cw Cooling seawater
31 sw Seawater
32 d Distillate
33 da Distillate from the distribution system
34 dr Distillate entering the mixers in the distribution system
35 dm Distillate temperature entering the mixers in the distribution system
36 vh Vapor consumed by pre-heater
37 gb Generated vapor by boiling
38 gf Generated vapor by flashing
39 f Feed water
40 fv Generated vapor by boiling and flashing
41 s Heating steam in the first effect
42 eff Effect
43 ph Pre-heater
44 v Heating steam in each effect
45 vc Vapor in the condenser
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18 **Figure captions**

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21 **Fig. 1.** Schematic diagram of MED plant at the Plataforma Solar de Almería
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23 **Fig. 2.** Flow diagram of a typical preheater (#i)
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25 **Fig. 3.** Flow diagram of the first effect
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27 **Fig. 4.** Flow diagram of the subgroup G2-1
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29 **Fig. 5.** Flow diagram of Subgroup G2-2
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33 **Fig. 7.** Flow diagram of the distillate distribution system
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35 **Fig. 8.** Flow diagram of the final condenser
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37 **Fig. 9.** Comparison between the model and actual values of the accumulated vapor generated by
38 boiling and flashing process (M_{fv})
39
40 **Fig. 10.** Comparison between the model and actual values of the brine mass leaving each effect
41 (M_b)
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43 **Fig. 11.** Gain Output Ratio for different brine temperatures in the first effect
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45 **Fig. 12.** Specific Area for different brine temperatures in the first effect
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Table 1

Input variables data

Feed water mass flow rate (M_f), kg/h	8000
Number of effects	14
Number of preheaters	13
Heating steam mass flow rate (M_s), kg/h	295.92
Heating steam temperature (T_s), °C	70.8
Feed water temperature in the first effect (T_f), °C	66.3
Seawater inlet temperature in the condenser ($T_{cw,in}$), °C	25
Seawater outlet temperature in the condenser ($T_{cw,out}$), °C	32.3

Table 2
Input variables data

Effect	Inlet Temperature, °C	
	Vapor, $T_v(i)$	Brine, $T_b(i)$
1	68	69
2	65.2	66.2
3	62.5	63.5
4	59.8	60.8
5	57.1	58.1
6	54.5	55.5
7	51.8	52.8
8	49.2	50.2
9	46.8	47.8
10	44.2	45.2
11	41.8	42.8
12	39.5	40.5
13	37.1	38.1
14	35	36

Table 3

Comparison between model and experimental values of the accumulated vapor and brine mass flow rate in each effect

Effect	Accumulated vapor mass flow rate, kg/h		Brine mass flow rate, kg/h	
	Model	Actual	Model	Actual
1	257	256.5	7743	7735
2	248	249.0	7495	7486
3	244	246.2	7251	7241
4	239	243.4	7012	6997
5	233	238.0	6779	6760
6	224	231.7	6555	6528
7	224	223.7	6331	6305
8	216	214.2	6115	6091
9	202	294.0	5913	5887
10	208	202.3	5705	5686
11	190	191.0	5515	5495
12	172	180.1	5343	5315
13	178	176.7	5165	5139
14	159	159.3	5006	4981

Table 4

Comparison between model and experimental values of the total distillate water production, the seawater inlet mass flow rate in the condenser, the Gain Output Ratio, the Recovery Ratio and the heat transfer areas of the effects, preheaters and condenser

Parameters	Model	Actual
M_{prod} (kg/h)	3003	2984
M_{sw} (kg/h)	15848	14558
GOR	10.2	9.7
RR	37.6	37.5
A_{eff} (m ²)	33.6	26.3
A_{ph} (m ²)	4.1	5
A_{c} (m ²)	13.1	18.3

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